

FLAGSHIP WORK PROGRAMME

SPOKE N4 – Montagna Digitale e Sostenibile

DELIVERABLE D1.0

NODES - Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

A. PROJECT INFORMATION

Acronym: SUMMER

Name of the project: SUsustainable Management of Mountain Energy and water Resources

Abstract: Mountain areas provide essential ecosystem services to downstream communities, being the source of water and energy resources necessary for sustaining our society. Also at a local scale, a large energy and water demand is required by various users in the Alpine area, like, for example, the tourism and skiing industries. The long-term objective of this part of the project is to accompany energy and water management into the digital era, showing how smart technology can boost the integrated management of water and energy systems. Digital technologies, combined with the power of 'big data' and AI-based analytics, drive unprecedented innovation in how energy and water utilities and companies manage these vital resources. To make the north-western Italy productive ecosystem ready to face this challenge, four specific applied research and innovation pathways are detailed in the following, pertaining with 1. Monitoring and forecasting water resources and energy productivity at the watershed scale; 2. Integrated management of energy production and use; 3. Risk-resilient Energy and Water Infrastructures; 4. Smart Energy and Water Distribution Systems.

Sectors/domains: Digital and sustainable mountain

Scientific Leader: Francesco Laio, Politecnico di Torino

1. Participants

List of participants

Participant No	Participant's Research Unit – Department	Research Themes and Skills involved in the project	Located in Mezzogiorno (Y/N)
Politecnico di Torino	DIATI	Flagship project coordination. Flood, heavy rainfall and fire risk assessment. Water resources assessment. Water distribution systems modeling.	N
	DENERG	Physical and data driven modelling of digital twins for the built environment and the energy systems, Modelling and optimization of grid- interactive efficient buildings	N
	DISEG	Gravitative hazards risk assessment. Structural modelling of elements at risk for vulnerability calculations.	N
	DAUIN	Data Driven Machine learning modelling for multi energy systems, Theory-Guided Data Science blending data-driven and domain-driven approaches, Physics-Informed Neural Networks, distributed co-simulation platform of multi energy systems, distributed software platforms for management of internet of things devices.	N

Università di Torino	Dip. Management	Integrated Management Systems as a framework for the integration of variables related to soil, snow, water quality and energy production.	N
	DIST	Meteorological variables, snow, soil moisture, infiltration capacity and permeability, droughts, landslides, erosion and avalanches. Sensors, IoT, satellite observations, data transmission	N
	Dipartimento di Scienze Agrarie, Forestali e Alimentari (DISAFA)	Soil and snow properties assessment. Soil erosion, water quality and snow avalanches investigation.	N
	Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra	Historical Meteorological Series and meteorological data (temperature, precipitation, snow), Digital monitoring and multiscale mapping of hydro-geodiversity and related abiotic ecosystem services	N
Università della Valle d'Aosta	Dipartimento di Scienze Economiche e Politiche	Economically integrated management of energy production and use	N
Fondazione LINKS	Centro per l'Osservazione della Terra AI, Data and Space	Application of Artificial Intelligence techniques for the extraction of value-added information from remote sensing imagery.	N
Fondazione Montagna Sicura	Area Ricerca Ghiacciai, Neve e Valanghe	Glaciers and snow avalanches: dynamics, cadastre, forecast	N

2. Geographical area of interest

Activities will be located in mountain areas in Northwestern Italy. The target area for building up a prototypical large-scale digital twin for energy and water management is the combination of left-tributaries catchments of Po river from Stura di Lanzo to Sesia (see Figure 1). Activities will not be limited to this target area but will also include specific case studies located in other mountain areas of Piemonte, Valle d'Aosta, and Western Lombardia (e.g.: three mountain catchments in Valle di Susa and in Cuneo Province, where climate is quite different than in the area shown in Figure 1). Of course

Figure 1. Target area for building up a prototypical large-scale digital twin for energy and water management: Stura di Lanzo, Malone, Orco, Dora Baltea and Sesia catchments

3. Coherence with Spoke topics and mission

Consistently with Cluster 4 of the Horizon Europe program and in accordance with the priorities of the National Research Programme (NRP) PNR 2021-2027 to ensure the implementation of the scientific research strategy lines, this flagship project intends to contribute to the main objectives of the "Digital, Industry, Aerospace"1 chapter as follows:

- OB1. To achieve a leadership in clean and climate-neutral industrial value chains, circular economy and climate-neutral digital systems and infrastructures.
- OB2. To achieve economic, social and environmental resilience.
- OB3: To develop an attractive, secure and dynamic data economy.
- OB4. To consolidate and enhance reliable digital and emerging technologies.

Actions are consistent with the sustainable mountain strategy of the S3 of the Valle d'Aosta Region following specialisation areas:

- **Technologies and systems to increase energy efficiency.**
 - Energy efficient machinery, equipment and production systems, including domotic regulation, control and monitoring systems;
 - Production of electronic components and integration of electronic systems.
- **Technologies and systems for the production, transmission and management of energy from renewable sources.**
 - New technologies, systems and components for production from renewable sources, aimed at achieving greater production efficiency, reducing emissions (in the context of biomass) or meeting specific usage requirements (e.g., architectural integration, climatic conditions, etc.);
 - Management, production regulation and/or failure monitoring systems aimed at optimising the O&M phases of new and existing plants;
 - Landscape and environmental integration systems of production plants.
- **Energy infrastructure, interconnections and smart energy systems, including storage systems.**
 - Energy production and consumption data monitoring and management systems and IoE (Internet of Energy) developments;
 - Water catchment, adduction and distribution infrastructures for different uses, including pumping; Innovative district heating network management systems, including integration of renewable energy sources and natural risk assessment;

- Development of systems and configurations to facilitate the deployment and enable the management of Energy Communities.

With reference to the S3 of the Piedmont Region, actions are consistent with the following specialisation areas of the green technologies, resources and materials strategy:

- **Resilient cities and territories.**
 - Sustainable design and implementation of products and processes, including for innovative ways of using them (e.g.: energy communities, green communities);
 - Solutions and technologies with smart functions for more efficient management of resources, services and management of natural and man-made risks;
 - Solutions that, through advanced technologies for the collection, analysis and processing of (large amounts of) static and dynamic data, including heterogeneous data, the use of communication networks, the implementation of predictive and decision support models, as well as the use of information sharing tools, allow monitoring, protection and safety of infrastructures, networks, devices, services and systems.
- **Urban services and utilities.**
 - Digital solutions for monitoring, analysis, management and protection, water, energy, gas and service distribution networks;
 - Digital solutions for optimising the demand for resources (water, energy, gas and services) capable of reducing waste through profiling and engagement of citizens and large consumers;
 - Systems for measuring consumption and monitoring the quality of water resources, control of water networks;
 - Active control and monitoring systems for critical infrastructures.
- **Clean energy.**
 - Innovative and sustainable technologies and solutions for energy production;
 - Technologies and solutions for the efficient use, recovery and storage of energy.

B. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

1. Objectives and methodology

Activities will pertain to four research modules, as detailed in the following Section C.

Title of the research module	Expected outcomes	Technology readiness level	Envisaged activities
Monitoring and forecasting water resources and energy productivity at the watershed scale	Monitoring and forecasting of hydro-meteorological variables as well as the assessment of relevant environmental conditioning factors for enhancing ecosystem efficiency and promoting valuable resources and energy management. Use of innovative sensors, remote-sensing platforms, data-transmission tools, as well as data-storage and data-management protocols to join the big-data revolution of monitoring and forecasting	TRL 4/5 to 6	research, demonstration, piloting
Integrated management of energy production and use.	Foster the potential of digitalization toward the efficient integration of variable renewables in the power system, by enabling grids to better match energy demand and production. Synchronizing energy production with that from renewables to accommodate higher share of variable renewables and accelerate the decarbonization of the electricity sector. Deployment of hardware systems and digital and modelling tools for the integrated management of energy and water resources	TRL 5 to 7	research, demonstration, piloting
Risk-resilient Energy and Water Infrastructures	Digitalization to lead to infrastructures of enhanced resilience by allowing fine-scale real-time monitoring of the existing risks, drought included, as well as by providing rapid and accurate assessment of asset condition and support decision-making and adaptation. 50-years global warming risk scenario maps and statistical analysis of climate and landslides/debris/avalanches data to support planning and management of infrastructures. Limiting the risk of cyber-attacks by building system-wide resilience to multiutility companies	TRL 4/5 to 6	research, demonstration, piloting
Smart Energy and Water Distribution Systems.	Development, implementation and commercialization of innovative smart-grid solutions through smart metering and digital connectivity tools that allow devices and equipment to be continuously monitored and connected to the grid, accompanied by digital models of the networks that enable proper management of the big data generated by the sensors.	TRL 4 to 6	research, demonstration, piloting, first market replication

2. Ambition

Over the coming decades, digital technologies are set to make energy and water systems around the world more connected, intelligent, efficient, reliable and sustainable. Stunning advances in data, analytics and connectivity are enabling a range of new digital applications. Digitalized energy and water systems in the future may be able to identify who needs energy and water and deliver it at the right time, in the right place and at the lowest cost. But getting everything right will not be easy. The long-term ambition of this flagship project is thus to accompany energy and water management into the digital era, showing how smart technology can boost the integrated management of water and energy systems. The project will generate collaborations between the research system, the production system and local institutions by enhancing research results, facilitating technology transfer and accelerating the digital transformation of businesses and production processes working towards an economic and environmental sustainability and social impact of the territories involved. In summary, SUMMER's ambition is favoring the adoption of digital solutions by companies and citizens within mountain areas of the NODES ecosystem, as a means of revitalizing economic activities in line with the ecological transition.

As mentioned in Section A3, the foreseen activities are fully consistent with the relevant smart specialization strategies of the three involved regions and fully synergic with other activities envisaged within the Next Generation Italia plan (PNRR), covering three major assets: Mission 1, Digitalization, innovation, competitiveness; Mission 2, Green Revolution and Ecological Transition; Mission 5, Social inclusion and cohesion. More specifically, the research and innovation program of Spoke 4 are synergic and complementary with the following PNRR initiatives:

- National Innovation Infrastructure for the “Simulation and Monitoring of the Energy System” that will see the involvement of Politecnico di Torino
- Extended partnership (Partenariato esteso) on natural and anthropogenic risk, seeing the involvement of Politecnico di Torino
- Extended partnership (Partenariato esteso) on energy transition, seeing the involvement of Politecnico di Torino (under evaluation)

3. Expected outcomes

The main goal of this flagship project is the rational management of resources and transition toward a larger use of non-fossil energy sources. Expected results will include:

- Innovative sensors, remote-sensing platforms, data-transmission tools for efficiently monitoring and forecasting water resources and energy productivity.
- Data-storage and data-management protocols and facilities for correctly handling the generated big data.
- Digital and modelling tools for the integrated management of energy and water resources, operable in remote mode, including Digital Twins and Building Information Modelling.
- Innovative solutions for increasing and better managing the energy storage capacity.
- Demonstrators of the potential of digital technologies - including Internet of Things, Point Clouds, Artificial Intelligence, GNSS and Satellite technologies - to lead to infrastructures of enhanced resilience.
- “Plug and play” and interoperable monitoring and optimization software for energy production plants and multi-utilities.
- Smart metering and digital connectivity tools allowing appliances and equipment to be monitored continuously and to be connected to the grid.
- Digital models of the transmission and distribution networks and innovative smart-grid solutions.

We expect this flagship project will significantly contribute to research, innovation, technology transfer and socio-economic growth, as demonstrated by the following KPIs.

Flagship project contributes to reach Spoke's KPI

In the following table we report the Flagship contribution to the Spoke's KPIs..

Actions		Key Indicator (Impact Indicator, Outcome Indicator, Output Indicator)	FLAGSHIP overall target
Research Booster	Impact	(Increase of) private and private investment in R&D, through research and innovative activities carried out jointly by universities and companies, in particular SMEs, operating in the area	
		(increase of) business potential in terms of creation and acceleration of high-tech start-ups, development of new/enhanced product/services and/or improved industrial process	
Research activities and Flagship Project	Outcome	Number of Pilot Line / Demonstrators / Prototypes	1
		Number of publications	29
		Number of registered IPR (patents, utility models, trademarks, industrial designs)	1
	Output	Number of flagship project	1
		Number of professor and researcher involved	14
		Personnel effort dedicated to Research and Innovation and Flagship Project (person/month in three years)	130

4. Research data management and management of other research outputs

Data and relevant information will be managed in full compliance with the Data Management Plan of the NODES ecosystem

5. Impacts, Innovation and Exploitation

According to EUSALP strategy, digitalization through connectivity and digital services can be a way to address the critical challenges of mountain areas such as depopulation, brain drain, physical barriers, accessibility to welfare and economic growth (www.alpine-region.eu). Based on this line of reasoning, this flagship project considers the use of digital technologies a way to improve the performance of enterprises located in mountain areas by reducing or resolving the critical issues identified in the EUSALP strategy. In addition, digital technologies can be a way to combat the brain drain by attracting and retaining skilled workers in mountain regions. Digitalization becomes important to an efficient and sustainable use of water and energy resources, to reduce travel and to make it easier living in mountain areas for people working for companies wherever located on the territory of the ecosystem (mountain and plain).

Industry participation

The flagship project will generate significant industrial impact in the NODES ecosystem through the digital transformation of some key activities in mountain areas. Digital transformation is brought forward through

different transmission channels. By providing innovative digital solutions for firms in the realm of smart working and digital compliance, it contributes to digital transformation of the economic fabric of the territory. New organizational forms leading to inflows of high-skilled workers from different part of the NODES ecosystem to the mountain areas generate the knowledge spillovers and new start-up. Demand for new services from delocalized working activities as well as the definition of new digital solutions for firms and citizens stimulates the creation of new innovative and digitally oriented firms. In the context of green development, innovation activities can not only promote the efficiency of resource allocation and enhance the core competitiveness but can also drive the high-quality socio-economic development of the region.

Large scale companies with strong economic footprint in mountain areas include multi-utilities and energy production companies, as for example IREN, CVA, EGEEA, Cogne Acciai Speciali, STMicroelectronics, Engineering, Heineken are an active part of our ecosystem. Starting from larger companies, the ecosystem will expand its benefits to SMEs, with a leap toward productivity and environmental sustainability boosted by digital transition; in the long term, the whole territory will benefit of the digital and ecological transition propelled by the initiatives proposed here.

6. Compliance with ethics requirement

The project complies with ethical principles and applicable international, EU, and national laws, including the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocols. Appropriate procedures, policies, and structures are in place to foster responsible practices, prevent questionable research practices and research misconduct, and handle allegations of breaches of ethical principles and standards.

All the NODES consortium members are well aware of the ethical aspects of the project and will take into account international, EU, and national legislation when collecting potentially sensitive personal data. To enable participants to make informed decisions, detailed documentation (e.g. informed consent and/or terms of participation) will be prepared on a case-by-case basis, outlining the information that will be gathered, the intended use within the project and any applicable risks associated with potential public dissemination. All data will only be stored, used and/or shared when participants and/or legal entities to which ownership of the data can be credited have given their express informed consent for publication; participants and/or legal entities will be given the option to allow the public dissemination of the data and/or to disseminate the data in an anonymous or traceable way. The treatment of personal information and sensitive data will be done in accordance with the relevant international, EU, and national legislation.

The activities proposed will not negatively impact:

- Climate change mitigation, as they will not lead to significant greenhouse gas emissions;
- Climate change adaptation, as they will not lead to an increased adverse impact on the current climate and the expected future climate;
- Sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources, as they are not detrimental to the good status or the good ecological potential of bodies of water, including surface water and groundwater, or the good environmental status of marine waters;
- Pollution prevention and control, as they will not lead to a significant increase in emissions of pollutants into air, water or land;
- Transition to a circular economy, as they will neither lead to significant inefficiencies in the use of materials nor the direct or indirect use of natural resources nor will they significantly increase the generation, incineration or disposal of waste;
- Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems are neither significantly detrimental to the good condition and resilience of ecosystems nor detrimental to the conservation status of habitats and species.

C. PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

1. Work plan

Research Module n. 1:	Start month: 1	End month: 36
Title: Monitoring and forecasting water resources and energy productivity at the watershed scale.		
Location in Mezzogiorno: Both North and South of Italy		
Leader:	LINKS	
Partners involved:	DIATI, DAUIN, UNITO, UNIBAS	
Type of action	Industrial Research	
Effort in person/months	65	
<p>Objective description: Enhancing ecosystem efficiency and promoting valuable resources and energy management by monitoring and forecasting of hydro-meteorological variables (precipitation, evapotranspiration, wind speed, solar radiation, discharge, snow cover and snow water equivalent, carbon budget, etc.) as well as the assessment of relevant environmental conditioning factors (soil physical properties, soil moisture, soil infiltration capacity, soil permeability, rock and permafrost stability, glacier mass balance, dust and organic compounds deposition, etc.). This is even more crucial with the electricity sector becoming more decentralized with the proliferation of small and distributed energy producers connected directly to the distribution grid. Other sectors, like for example the agricultural, water supply, skiing and risk insurance industries, likewise strongly depend on innovative digital monitoring and forecasting systems. The challenge posed by these systems is especially harsh in mountain environments, typically characterized by low connectivity and accessibility conditions.</p>		
<p>Summary of the activities envisaged (provide measurable indicators, if available): The activities will focus on bridging the gap currently present in the monitoring of meteorological variables in mountain basins. Precipitation in liquid form can be measured with relatively high accuracy, however, as soon as it turns to snowfall various difficulties arise. For mountain regions, the amount of snow is an important piece of information. It serves to estimate the danger of avalanches, to plan road clearance or to determine meltwater quantities that have a major influence on the water cycle. Difficulties are mainly due to the uncertainty in the estimation of snowpack density and the correct quantification of its depth and spatial spread in complex orographic conditions, as well as the impact of mineral dust and biological matters on the snowmelting rate. Furthermore, the lack of data in the mountain area has not yet made it possible to accurately model the accumulation and melting phenomena which are essential for forecasting water availability during spring and summer seasons. We plan to address this issue through development of remote sensing platforms (e.g. ground observations, aerial and satellite data and UAVs), data transmission tools, innovative sensors and data storage and management protocols, which will be the subject of a synergistic effort within the NODES ecosystem (involving academic entities, multi-utility companies and innovative SMEs) to join the big-data revolution of monitoring and forecasting. To test innovative and traditional sensors, one or more test fields will be chosen in which to measure the characteristics of the snowpack and model accumulation and melting phenomena. In situ data are required for calibration and validation of remote sensing data, to enhance snow hydrological monitoring and modeling and to assess relevant environmental conditioning factors (bedrock, soil, landforms, glacier dynamics). All the data measurements from the sensors will be transmitted and stored through the development of a dedicated network. Part of the research will be developed to better define the hydrological response of small and very small hydrographic basins, with reference both to the production of the water resource and the generation of extreme hydrological events. To this end, we will also make use of the instruments available in the experimental basin of Fiumarella di Corleto (Val d'Agri), equipped for the measurement of many meteorological-climatic</p>		

quantities and soil humidity, and for which innovative hydrological models with high technological potential are available.

The research activities will be performed through 3 actions:

Action 1: innovative sensors.

Innovative sensors to estimate the SWE. We plan to explore the potential of optical fiber and Cosmic rays to continuously measure SWE and snow temperature. In the test field a distributed network of optical fibers and CRNS probes (cosmic ray neutron sensing) will be installed and tested.

Innovative methods to measure snow distribution and depth. We plan to develop an innovative network of sensors to measure the snow depth on a vast surface. In fact, traditional snow level sensors are very precise but they measure the snow depth in only one location. Nonetheless, the accumulation of snow in a complex orography (basin surrounded by high mountains) is almost always extremely heterogeneous and a single but punctual measurement, albeit very precise, can be largely non-representative of the total amount of snow.

Action 2: monitoring. In this action we will integrate the ground-based measurements from innovative and traditional sensors with remote sensing survey at scale of basin-watershed. Water, snow, carbon and energy fluxes will be measured as well, investigating the interactions of geochemical, physical, geological and biological processes such as rock weathering, soil formation, groundwater dynamics and biogeochemical cycling. Design and development of proper processing chains, integrating SoA AI techniques, to generate value-added products based on multi-spectral/temporal/scale remotes sensing datasets (satellite and/or aerial) to support the project large-scale Digital Twin development. In particular, DL frameworks devoted to segmentation and classification tasks will be specifically conceived and developed to extract selected features from 3D information derived from aerial photogrammetric and/or satellite datasets acquired in the project. Moreover, proper ML/DL techniques will be applied on multi-spectral/temporal/scale remotes sensing datasets (satellite and/or aerial), for vegetation and land cover monitoring in order to investigate and map the main dynamics of the following territorial phenomena: land degradation and fragmentation, deforestation, built-up area modification and soil sealing.

Action 3: data analysis and forecasting. In this action we will check the functionality of the data transmission, development of procedures for data analysis and validation of multitemporal data. Data from existing networks and historical archives will also be used. Data assimilation of ground-based and remotely sensed observations for water, snow and carbon balance model simulations we'll be stored and used for developing forecasting tools, theory-guided data science models for advanced analytics, simulation, forecasting. Scientific publications on the innovation in sensors, on data integration and modeling are expected.

State of the Art and technological knowledge involved (if any):

Snow is a fundamental water resource, threatened by climate change. The decrease of water storage in the snowpack can have relevant impacts on water supply for mountain and lowland areas that rely on snow melting. The characterisation of the snow cover in terms of spatial distribution, seasonal - interannual evolution, and optical properties supports the description of melting processes. In this context, the optical properties of the surface in terms of snow cover occurrence and its microphysical characteristics (snow grain size and shape, impurities contents such as mineral dust and biological matter, etc) are key elements that control the dynamics of the snow cover melting. Among the different observed snow-related variables, Snow Water Equivalent (SWE) plays a crucial role, since it is critical for flood and drought prediction, hydropower management, snowmaking, ecological monitoring, avalanche forecasting, and mountain aquifer recharge. Despite the relevance of SWE, fewer direct measurements are available for this variable than for snow depth. Mountain environment lacks a systematic assessment of soil moisture and temperature data as well, and of soil permeability, in order to obtain an integrated framework for water, snow and carbon balance modeling and forecasting.

Output and results:

- Innovative sensors, remote-sensing platforms, data-transmission tools for efficient monitoring and forecasting of water resources and energy productivity.
- Data-storage and data-management protocols and facilities for correctly handling and representation of the generated big data.
- Digital and modelling tools for the integrated management of energy and water resources, operable in remote mode, including Digital Twins and Building Information Modelling.
- Definition of the hydrological response of small and very small hydrographic basins, with reference both to the production of the water resource and to the generation of extreme hydrological events.

Expected investments in infrastructures and instruments, and subcontracting (if any):

- 1) Electromagnetic geophysical devices (Time Domain Electromagnetic device and Time Domain Reflectometer) for characterisation and monitoring of snow and rocks;
- 2) Installation of distributed fiber optical system for measurements of temperature and density of snow;
- 3) Network of sensors to measure the snow depth on a vast surface
- 4) Updating infrastructure at the LTER Istituto Mosso site and data networking with the Garstelet Glacier for data collection from an innovative probe to infer temporally continuous SWE in the high-mountain environment.
- 5) Integrating the actual monitoring instrumentation in the experimental basin of Fiumarella di Corleto

Research Module n. 2:	Start month:1	End month:36
Title: Integrated management of energy production and use.		
Location in Mezzogiorno: N		
Leader:	DENERG	
Partners involved:	DIATI, DAUIN, UNITO, DISEG, LINKS, UNIVDA	
Type of action	Industrial Research	
Effort in person/months	55	
<p>Objective description:</p> <p>The introduction of more and smarter sensors to monitor various parameters, ranging from operating conditions to equipment status, allows for the implementation of energy management strategies including advanced control and energy information services such as the identification and diagnosis of system inefficiencies, the development of operation and maintenance schedules. The program aims to develop plug-and-play monitoring and optimization software that can be easily implemented and used across a wide variety of processes, from buildings to energy production plants, multi-energy systems and utilities. To this aim, different modelling approaches will be adopted. Forward models will be tailored in order to perform energy scenario analyses. Innovative Artificial Intelligence models will be developed to implement energy management strategies, also by blending traditional data-driven learning with theory-based and physics informed intelligent systems.</p> <p>Within this research module we will also foster the potential of digitalization toward the efficient integration of intermittent renewables (including solar PV and wind power) in the energy systems, by enabling grids to better match energy demand from users (e.g. buildings) and production from either RES and/or traditional sources. This will be done taking into account that synchronizing energy production with that from stable renewables as hydropower is another crucial issue, extremely relevant to accommodate a higher share of intermittent renewables and accelerate the decarbonization of the electricity sector.</p>		
<p>Summary of the activities envisaged (provide measurable indicators, if available):</p> <p>BIM modelling, BEM modelling and digital twins of infrastructures and plants are essential tools deployed within our innovation ecosystem for proper design and real-time management of water-energy systems. Hardware systems and digital and modelling tools for the integrated management of energy and water resources. Some case studies typical of mountain areas (i.e. small mountain communities, snowmaking</p>		

systems and ski facilities, high mountain huts, etc.) will be chosen as case studies to apply the developed methodologies.

Energy and water needs: preliminary, the characterization and forecasting of energy demand in contexts with various types of users will be assessed through both physics-based and data-driven-based modelling approaches, such as Engineering direct models and Artificial Intelligence models (Physics-Informed Neural Networks and Theory-Guided Data Science approaches). Models will be developed also for all the possible water uses (drinking water, domestic hot water, irrigation, industrial, etc) in terms of quantity and related energy needs.

Energy production: data and models from the previous activity will be used here to predict water availability during the year. Meteorological data from ARPA Piemonte, Photovoltaic Geographical Information Systems (e.g. PVGIS) and weather communities (e.g. wunderground) will be used to estimate PV and wind energy hourly availability for every case study. In order to estimate PV potential, new Computer Vision techniques, based on machine and deep learning and applied to multitemporal satellite data, is foreseen with the aim of monitoring existing photovoltaic systems (both industrial and civil) and for analyzing rooftop.

Integrating production, consumption through storage: integrated models of production and consumption of energy and water used on the territory will be developed, to maximize RES energy exploitation, for each case study. For this purpose, adequate energy storage systems (pumped hydro, PH, and hot water tanks) will be dimensioned to increase the use of RES. In the context of storage, since the needed volumes for PH can be very large, we will explore the possibility of using the abandoned quarries, which abound in our mountains, as underground reservoir. Moreover, innovative solutions aimed to increase the energy flexibility, including Demand Side Management (DSM) strategies, with particular attention to the optimization of the energy storage operation and renewable energy exploitation, will be explored.

A hybrid software-in-the-loop and hardware-in-the-loop multi-model co-simulation infrastructure for multi-energy systems will be explored to test new solutions in a virtual test-bed for scenario. It will allow the interconnection of heterogeneous pure software simulators with real-time hardware simulators in a shared and distributed co-simulation environment. The virtual representation of the equivalent real-world environment (i.e., the digital twin) consists of different plug-and-play models to simulate the different entities in the environment (e.g., renewable energy systems, storage systems, etc.) to define different energy scenarios to be evaluated by the different stakeholders. To manage both Internet of Things (IoT) devices and the heterogeneous data coming from them in (near-) real-time, a distributed smart metering software platform will be explored aiming at i) fostering novel services, ii) feeding the digital twin and its models and iii) cooperating with the co-simulation platform during scenario simulations.

State of the Art and technological knowledge involved (if any):

The challenges posed by climate change, the digital and energy transition together with increasing penetration of IOT and ICT technologies are contributing to revolutionize the paradigm of the energy and water management. In this context, the increasing demand of energy with the consequent need to enhance efficiency and flexibility, the penetration of renewable energy sources and decentralized multi-energy systems, are pushing for the progressive introduction of integrated grid-interactive building and users-. The implementation of data-driven and engineering models for the optimal management of energy production and use makes it possible to rely on multi-objective problem formulation by solving simultaneously technical, economic, and environmental problems by leveraging on real-time control procedures, forecast modelling and stochastic-based decision analysis.

Digital twins have emerged as a promising solution in the path toward energy transition and decarbonization in several fields. Digital twins are virtual representations of an object or system and how it changes over time. In this way, the virtual and physical states are synchronized, several parameters can be evaluated in different scenarios, and the decision-making process is facilitated. Examples of applications of digital twins are in energy-efficient manufacturing, in the energy system design and the renewable energy sector.

Output and results:

- Digital and modelling tools for the integrated management of energy and water resources, operable in remote mode, including Digital Twins and Building Information Modelling.
- Assessment and characterization of energy demand for different end-uses and at different scales

(from single building to districts of buildings and users);

- Development of data driven energy management strategies aimed to enhance the energy flexibility at demand side and to provide services to the energy grids;
- Data-storage and data-management integration for correctly handling the generated data of various types, from different sources and time scales;
- “Plug and play” and interoperable monitoring, modelling and optimization digital twin platform for energy production and use.
- Multi-modelling distributed co-simulation platform for multi-energy systems

Expected investments in infrastructures and instruments, and subcontracting (if any):

- Computing resources
- Third party services (e.g. wunderground)
- IoT sensors
- Subcontracting to develop the platform

Research Module n. 3:	Start month: 1	End month: 36
Title: Risk-resilient Energy and Water Infrastructures.		
Location in Mezzogiorno: Both North and South of Italy		
Leader:	UNITO	
Partners involved:	DENERG, DIATI, DISEG, FMS, LINKS, UNIBAS	
Type of action	Industrial Research	
Effort in person/months	90	
<p>Objective description: Water adduction, water collected in reservoirs and energy transmission systems in mountain environments are typically subject to multiple natural hazards such as landslides, accelerated soil erosion, earthquakes, snow avalanches, glacial collapse, river floods, which can induce critical interruption and/or reduced efficiency in the services provided by the utility companies. Through digitalization, infrastructure systems can become more resilient, as well as provide rapid, accurate asset conditions assessments to support decision-making and adaptation. Droughts as well are challenging energy and water supply utilities. Digitalization can help in a better knowledge and management of their effects.</p>		
<p>Summary of the activities envisaged (provide measurable indicators, if available): Within this innovation ecosystem we will demonstrate the potential of digital technologies - including Internet of Things, Digital Twins, Point Clouds, Artificial Intelligence, GNSS and Satellite technologies, Building Information Modelling, Innovative networks of sensors and Risk Maps - to lead to infrastructures of enhanced resilience. All the aforementioned technologies will be used in some test sites for real time monitoring. Thanks to real time measurements, forecasting models and digitalization, a multi-hazard framework accounting for various gravitative hazards (snow avalanche, landslides) on energy distribution systems will be formulated. The risk analysis will focus on the interaction of the hazard on the components of the transmission system (poles, cables) to identify the best digital solution and measurement device to enhance the resilience of power grid elements. Attention will be devoted to the accessibility of energy production plants (e.g., dams) during winter thanks to tailored risk evaluation assessments enhanced by real-time measurements. An analysis of long-term historical satellite datasets will be carried out to map hazards related to main natural disasters (such as flood, landslides, fires, droughts, etc.) in order to support the evaluation and modelling of risks affecting critical infrastructures, industries and assets (e.g., power grids, viaducts etc.). In the context of the Fiumarella di Corleto hydrographic basin, geological surveys will be carried out covering the basin on a 1:10,000 scale and using the orthophotos returned by light technologies (drones).</p>		

<p>Two large landslides will be investigated on the left side of the valley which they invaded the valley floor causing the formation of a temporary barrier lake upstream.</p>
<p>State of the Art and technological knowledge involved (if any): Energy and water infrastructures are of primary importance in mountain areas. The lack of redundancy in distribution networks makes such systems more vulnerable and less resilient. Energy distribution systems are usually located in steep slopes and are subjected to multiple natural hazards, say snow avalanches, landslides and rockfalls. Water supply, agriculture and other water uses are also prone to such hazards, and also to recent extreme droughts. The studies on the vulnerability of such elements are limited to common hazards (earthquake, seism), which are not frequent in mountain environments. The knowledge on the effects of typical mountain risks (snow avalanche, rockfall, landslides) on power systems is limited. Meanwhile, mountain hazards are site specific and the outputs of the modelling are largely dependent on the quality of the input data measured onsite. Techniques and frameworks merging measured data, modelling and outputs with real-time update are needed to tackle such hazards.</p>
<p>Output and results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital and modelling tools for the integrated management of energy and water resources, operable in remote mode, including Digital Twins and Building Information Modelling. • Demonstrators of the potential of digital technologies - including Internet of Things, Point Clouds, Artificial Intelligence, GNSS and Satellite technologies - to lead to infrastructures of enhanced resilience. • Geological surveys covering the basin on a 1:10,000 scale for two large landslides of the Fiumarella di Corleto hydrographic basin.
<p>Expected investments in infrastructures and instruments, and subcontracting (if any):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complementing the existing sites of Chevrere, Cogne, Bussoleno, Nivolet with sensors for flux measurements • Dynamic analyses on the propagation of snow avalanches and other gravitative phenomena in the selected test sites • Installation of Lidar and radar systems (InSAR) to monitor the slopes subjected to avalanche and landslide hazards • Installation of sensors on elements at risk to assess in real time their vulnerability

Research Module n. 4:	Start month: 1	End month: 36
Title: Smart Energy and Water Distribution Systems.		
Location in Mezzogiorno: N		
Leader:	DIATI	
Partners involved:	DENERG	
Type of action	Industrial Research	
Effort in person/months	30	
<p>Objective description: The increasing water demand for hydropower and the impact of climate change on the availability of water requires a dramatic re-thinking how to keep the lights (and the taps) on, while both are making the best use of new energy (and water) sources and keeping infrastructure costs down. Instead of only extending and reinforcing physical infrastructure, which is extremely costly and disruptive to local communities, new management policies and systems are needed to arrive at decisions that narrow the discrepancies between stakeholders (i.e. energy producers, drinking water suppliers and irrigation consortia). To support these decision-making approaches, it is necessary to implement a better knowledge of the systems that use the water resource at the basin scale. Complementary, IT solutions must be developed, adding communication, sensors, and automation, allowing distribution-system operators to actively manage the varying generation and demand. This combination of solutions is what is commonly referred to as a smart grid. Digitalization of the energy and water distribution networks will prospectively increase the security of supply, improve the quality of service, and better respond to demand from customers.</p>		

Summary of the activities envisaged (provide measurable indicators, if available):

The relevant actions include a) a better spatial-temporal description of water availability, distribution networks, and the needs of end users, b) development and adoption of smart metering and digital connectivity tools allowing water availability and flow rate to be monitored continuously and connected to the grid, c) digital models of the networks allowing a proper management of the big data generated from the sensors. The NODES ecosystem aims at promoting the development, deployment, and commercialization of innovative smart-grid related solutions. To simplify the approach two actions will be implemented separately

Action 1: Energy and drinking water distribution systems.

Drinking water and energy are interdependent on each other. Energy is required to supply water to the distribution system while, at the same time, water is needed for power generation in any natural or artificial system. In a water supply system, energy is consumed for source water extraction, transmission, treatment, and distribution. Moreover, energy can be produced when there is an excess of energy in the distribution network, which is not uncommon in mountain aqueducts. The main purpose of this action is to study, at a local and basin scale, a) the potential conflicts between hydroelectric and potable use, b) create and interconnect networks for the production, storage and distribution of water and energy, and c) develop new measurement IT tools and adapt existing ones to provide the data necessary for the smart network.

Action 2: Energy production and irrigation distribution networks.

Reservoirs are generally built with multiple functions in mind, and irrigation and hydroelectricity generation are often the main functions. While reservoir operations for hydroelectricity production might support irrigation, there are also well-known cases where hydroelectricity production reduces water availability for irrigation. Reservoirs buffer the fluctuations of natural streamflow and can provide reliable water supply for irrigation during dry periods. At the same time, the owner of the hydroelectric plant tends to maximize the economic profit of the power plant which is a function of the energy produced and the trend in energy prices on the market. The optimal allocation of the resource among the users must be based on an excellent knowledge of the current and future hydrological cycle and of the uses of water for hydroelectric and irrigation purposes. The main purpose of this action is a) to reconstruct the network consisting of storage, transport, distribution and the related uses for hydroelectric and irrigation purposes, b) to develop decision-making approaches that take into account the information of the network and c) data from new IT tools and methods that will be developed during the next three years.

Both actions will be implemented using the meteorological and hydrological data provided by ARPA Piedmont and the historical data provided by the managers of hydroelectric plants and irrigation consortia. Once the current situation is photographed, some of the most reliable climate scenarios will be used to understand how global change could impact water availability and to develop network adaptation strategies.

State of the Art and technological knowledge involved (if any):

Conflicting water use alternatives among different stakeholders who share a common source of water has been identified in many national and international basins around the world. Such conflicts have lead water managers develop new management policies and systems to arrive at decisions that narrow the discrepancies between stakeholders.

Output and results:

- Digital models of the transmission and distribution networks and innovative smart-grid solutions.
- Smart metering and digital connectivity tools allowing appliances and equipment to be monitored continuously and to be connected to the grid.
- Innovative solutions for increasing and better managing the water storage capacity and energy production.

Expected investments in infrastructures and instruments, and subcontracting (if any):

- Computing resources
- IoT sensors

Table - List of Deliverables

NUM	OUTPUTS/DELIVERABLE NAME	TYPE*	SHORT DESCRIPTION	LEAD PARTICIPANT	DISSEMINATION LEVEL**	DUE DATE
D1	Flagship work programme	R	Description of the flagship activities	DIATI	PU	M2
D2	Technical Call fiche	OTHER	Cal Fiche for hiring researchers and technicians	POLITO, UNITO, UNIVDA	PU	M2
D3	Geodatabase structure	OTHER	Geodatabase structure for digital twin implementation	LINKS, DAUIN	SEN	M6
D4	First progress report	R	First progress report on research activities	LINKS (module 1), DENERG (module 2), UNITO (module 3), DIATI (module 4)	PU	M12
D5	First dataset delivery	DATA	First delivery of the integrated dataset form modules 1-4	DIATI	PU	M12
D6	Digital twin (beta version)	DEM	First release of the digital twin with specific functionalities for the four modules	LINKS (module 1), DENERG (module 2), UNITO (module 3), DIATI (module 4)	SEN	M18
D7	Innovative sensors (first release)	DEM	First release of the innovative sensors developed within the four modules	LINKS (module 1), DENERG (module 2), UNITO (module 3), DIATI (module 4)	SEN	M18
D8	Second progress report	R	Second progress report on research activities	LINKS (module 1), DENERG (module 2), UNITO (module 3), DIATI (module 4)	PU	M24
D9	Second dataset delivery	DATA	Second delivery of the integrated dataset form modules 1-4	DIATI	SEN	M24
D10	Geological survey	DATA	Geological survey of the Fiumarella di Corleto hydrographic basin	Università della Basilicata	SEN	M25
D11	Model of a	OTHER	Model of a	Università della	PU	M30

	hydrological response		hydrological response of small and very small basins	Basilicata		
D12	Final report	R	Final report on research activities	LINKS (module 1), DENERG (module 2), UNITO (module 3), DIATI (module 4)	SEN	M36
D13	Final dataset delivery	DATA	Final delivery of the integrated dataset form modules 1-4	DIATI	PU	M36
D14	Digital twin (final version)	DEM	Final release of the digital twin with specific functionalities for the four modules	LINKS (module 1), DENERG (module 2), UNITO (module 3), DIATI (module 4)	SEN	M36
D15	Innovative sensors (final release)	DEM	Final release of the innovative sensors developed within the four modules	LINKS (module 1), DENERG (module 2), UNITO (module 3), DIATI (module 4)	SEN	M36

- Type -Use one of the following codes: R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports) DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc. DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc. DMP: Data management plan ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues. SECURITY: Deliverables related to security issues OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.
- Dissemination level - Use one of the following codes: Use one of the following codes: PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web; SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Spoke Consortium Agreement and Data Management Plan.

Table - List of Project Milestones

NUM	MILESTONE NAME	RELATED WORK MODULES	DUE DATE (MONTH)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
1	Launch of research	all	M6	Deliverables and results
2	First Dataset Delivery	all	M12	Deliverables and results
3	Digital Twin & Innovative Sensor - First Releases	all	M18	Deliverables and results
4	Second Dataset Delivery	all	M24	Deliverables and results
5	Digital Twin & Innovative Sensor - Final Releases	all	M36	Deliverables and results

2. Critical risks for implementation

DESCRIPTION OF RISK (INDICATE LEVEL OF LIKELIHOOD, AND SEVERITY: LOW/MEDIUM/HIGH)	INTERMEDIATE WORK MODULE(S) INVOLVED	PROPOSED RISK-MITIGATION MEASURES
Partners related risks – underperforming, leaving the project, key-personnel temporarily not available [Low/medium]	all	Flexible project management structure allows a quick shift of resources to alternative project partners. Furthermore, partners are involved in related areas, with more than a single staff member, ensuring an immediate substitution.
Planning problems: resources underestimated, project timing not appropriate, further experts needed, deliverables/milestones delayed [Medium/Medium]	all	Potential solutions are rearrangement of resources among partners, change of the project plan within the self-assessment activities, and ensuring timely implementation of corrective actions.
New research results cause priority shifts – it may become necessary to change the project’s direction due to dynamically changing situations, with a shift in priorities resulting. [Low/Medium]	all	The Consortium as a whole and the Scientific Manager will perform a thorough monitoring of research results potentially affecting the direction of the project, and track regional changes in policies, assuring alignment of the project with the current situation.
Solutions developed do not scale or yield much lower performance improvements than envisioned [Low/High]	all	Advancements made across pilot applications will be closely monitored by an outlined benchmarking and profiling strategy. Thus, we will react early on possible lack of scalability issues.
Unforeseen problems related the availability of data to be used by use cases [Low/Medium]	all	Data availability is crucial. To mitigate this risk, appropriate data harvesting mechanisms are set in place to track progress of availability of data.
Failed or insufficient exploitation of results [Low/High]	all	The hub and spoke structure of the ecosystem will allow to develop synergies and to control possible failures, thus maximizing exploitation

3. Project costs

PARTICIPANT NO	COST (€)	JUSTIFICATION
Personnel cost	1038701	230 person/months of structured personnel 90 person/months non-structured personnel
Goods, equipment, research instrumentations	378594	Sensors for monitoring water and energy resources. Hardware facilities for managing large datasets. IoT tools
Subcontracting	62544	Outsourcing activities for digital twin building and maintenance
Total	1479839	

